

SHAPE CONTROL OF STRUCTURES WITH PZT ACTUATORS USING GENETIC ALGORITHMS

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SUMMARY: The use of piezoelectric actuators for shape control and correction of static deformations is considered. Genetic algorithms (GA) are implemented to calculate the optimal layout and the optimal voltages, applied to the piezoelectric actuators glued in the structure, which minimise the error between the achieved and the pre-defined shape. The need of an optimisation algorithm able to solve efficiently this problem without imposing a large number of requirements and restrictions lead us to use these algorithms. Simulations and experimental measurements are compared for different geometry with different boundary conditions and pre-defined displacement fields. Experimental results consider only beam and plate structures made of isotropic materials, however the developed methodology is general and can be applied to a more complex geometry made of orthotropic materials.

KEYWORDS: shape control, genetic algorithms, actuator layout, optimum design, PZT actuators, adaptive structures.

INTRODUCTION

Shape control of flexible structures can improve the aerodynamic performance of lifting surfaces, correct the shape of antennas or mirrors as well as compensate quasi-static displacements due to temperature or humidity variations. The most common methods to control the shape of a structure consists in embedding piezoelectric materials in it. Crawley and De Luis (1987)¹ developed static and dynamic analytical models for structures with distributed sensors and actuators, glued or embedded in the structure. These models are able to predict, a priori, the response of the structure. Koconis *et al* (1994)^{2,3} addressed the shape control problem: calculation of the shape of the structure due to specified voltages and calculation of the required voltages to produced a pre-defined shape. Chandrashekhara and Varadarajan (1997)⁴ used the Lagrange multiplier approach to determine the optimal actuator voltages needed to attain the pre-defined shape of a composite beam.

This paper proposes the use of a straightforward method, based on finite element analysis and GA, to calculate the optimal position and the optimal actuation voltages of the piezoceramic (PZT) elements bonded on a structure in order to induce that same structure to deform in a certain pre-defined way. The only constraints are the saturation voltages of the piezoelectric elements and the maximum number of actuators allowed within the structure. Simulation and experimental measurements validate the procedure.

MATHEMATICAL MODEL AND OPTIMISATION ALGORITHM

Shape control problems can be considered quasi-static in the presence of slow time varying disturbances. In this case the displacement field can be easily computed as a function of the stiffness of the structure and of the applied actuation voltages, $\{\phi\}$, by^{5,6}

$$\{q\} = [K_{mm}]^{-1}[K_{em}]\{\phi\} \quad (1)$$

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The determination of the mechanical stiffness, $[K_{mm}]$, and the coupled electrical/mechanical stiffness matrices, $[K_{em}]$, is based in the Mindlin theory of plates. The equations of motion were discretised in four-node elements with 6 degrees of freedom per node plus an electrical degree of freedom per piezoelectric layer.⁷

When considering plate elements, the shape of a structure is mainly described by the shape of its mid-plane, which itself is described by the transverse displacement of the finite element mesh nodes. Therefore, the error between the pre-defined displacement field function and the achieved displacement field, can be defined as the sum of the errors at the n nodal points, and the fitness or objective function, J , is then given by

$$J^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n (\gamma_i - q_i)^2 \quad (2)$$

where γ_i is the pre-defined displacement at the i -th node and q_i the transverse displacement at the same node. This objective function gives an estimate of the variance of the values with respect to the pre-defined displacement. The shape control problem, or the correction of static deformations, of a given structure with a given layout of piezoelectric actuators, consists, therefore, in finding a set of actuator voltages, ϕ_i , that minimises the error between the desired shape function and the achieved one (Equation 2) subjected to the following constraint

$$\phi_{min} \leq \phi_i \leq \phi_{max} \quad (3)$$

where ϕ_i is the actuation voltage of the i -th actuator and ϕ_{min} and ϕ_{max} the lower and upper saturation voltages. Equations 2 and 3 represent the minimisation formulation problem - fitness function and constraints - to be solved by genetic algorithms.

These algorithms are stochastic optimisation techniques based in the natural evolutionary process and on the *survival-of-the-fittests*^{8,9}. They are iterative procedures which maintain a population of candidate solutions of the problem called *chromosomes*. Each chromosome is constituted by a number of individual structures called *genes*. During each iteration step, *generation*, each solution is evaluated to give some measure of its *fitness*, and, on the basis of those evaluations a new population of candidate solutions is formed. Then *crossover* and *mutation* operators are applied to this population allowing recombination and exchange of genetic material (Figure 1).

Figure 1. General structure of genetic algorithms.

Crossover is the main genetic operator under which two chromosomes, called *parents*, combine portions of their internal representation generating new chromosomes called *offsprings*. The crossover probability, p_c , associated to this operator, is defined as the ratio of the number of offspring produced in each generation to the population size. Mutation is a background operator that produces a random alteration of a gene. The mutation probability, p_m , gives the expected number of mutated genes, and controls the rate at which new genes are introduced in the population for trial.

The process by which strings are copied to the new population according to their objective function values or fitness is called *reproduction* or *selection*. The new solutions are the result of a random selection procedure that ensures, at each generation, that the "good" solutions reproduce, while the relatively "bad" ones die.¹⁰ An *elitist strategy* can be employed to avoid that the best solution in the population disappears due to sampling errors, crossover or mutation. The reproduction operator can be implemented in the algorithm in several ways, of which, the *tournament* selection procedure is one of the most commonly used and the one adopted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The procedure to find the optimal voltages of a structure in order to modify its shape was experimentally verified. The first experimental set-up comprises 2 different structures: an aluminium beam (clamped-free and clamped-clamped) and an aluminium plate (clamped-free). Then, the algorithm was slightly modified in order to accommodate also the determination of the optimal localisation of the piezoelectric actuators.

Experimental results: aluminium beam with 3 PZT

This experimental set-up comprises an aluminium beam with three bonded piezoceramics. Figure 2 presents schematically the layout of the beam for two different boundary conditions: clamped-free and clamped-clamped.

Figure 2. Layout of the aluminium beam, 1.0 mm thick, together with the piezoelectric elements, 0.3 mm thick, used in the experiment. Units are in mm.

The electro-mechanical properties given by the manufacturer of the piezoceramic elements (PX5-N from Philips Components) are presented in Table 1. The saturation voltage was set to ± 150 Volt.

Displacement measurements were done by a non-contact capacity displacement sensor (MC900 Fogale nanotech). With a 5 mm measurement range the sensor had a maximum resolution of $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ at 400Hz.

Clamped-free aluminium beam

Considering the clamped-free geometry two different displacement fields were arbitrarily chosen. Boundary conditions and magnitude of displacements compatible with the dimensions of the structures were the only two criteria to be fulfilled. The actuation voltages applied to each of the 3 piezoelectric elements in order to match the pre-defined displacement fields were calculated by GA. A population size of 25

Table 1. Material properties for the PX5-N piezoceramic material (data from the manufacturer). $[C^E]$ is the matrix of elastic coefficients at constant electric field, $[d]$ the piezoelectric module matrix, $[\epsilon]$ the dielectric constants matrix evaluated at constant stress and ρ the material density.

$C_{11}^E [N/m^2]$	13.11×10^{10}	$d_{31} [m/V]$	-215×10^{-12}
$C_{12}^E [N/m^2]$	7.984×10^{10}	$d_{33} [m/V]$	500×10^{-12}
$C_{13}^E [N/m^2]$	8.439×10^{10}	$d_{15} [m/V]$	515×10^{-12}
$C_{33}^E [N/m^2]$	12.31×10^{10}	$\epsilon_{11}^t / \epsilon_0$	1800
$C_{44}^E [N/m^2]$	2.564×10^{10}	$\epsilon_{33}^t / \epsilon_0$	2100
$C_{66}^E [N/m^2]$	2.564×10^{10}	$\rho [Kg/m^3]$	7800

Table 2. Pre-defined displacement field and actuation voltages obtained by GA (clamped-free aluminium beam). L is the length of the beam and x the longitudinal co-ordinate.

	Displacement Field	$V_{piezo1} [V]$	$V_{piezo2} [V]$	$V_{piezo3} [V]$
Case 1	$\gamma(x) = 0.0002(\frac{x}{L})^2$	17	36	26
Case 2	$\gamma(x) = 0.0004(\frac{x}{L})^2$	34	72	51

individuals, a probability of crossover equal to 0.85, a probability of mutation equal to 0.15 and a maximum number of generations of 15000 were considered in the calculations. Table 2 shows the pre-defined displacement fields and the actuation voltages obtained by the optimisation algorithm.

Figures 3 and 4 show the comparison between the two pre-defined displacement fields, simulation results from finite element calculations and experimental measurements.

Figure 3. Case1:clamped-free. Comparison between the pre-defined shape, simulation results and experimental measurements.

Figure 4. Case2:clamped-free. Comparison between the pre-defined shape, simulation results and experimental measurements.

In general, a very good agreement is obtained. The standard deviation between the pre-defined results and the simulation ones and between the pre-defined results and the experimental ones was calculated. For case 1 values of 0.0021 mm and 0.0073 mm were obtained while for case 2 one obtains 0.0042 mm and 0.024 mm, respectively. For both cases, experimental results are more dispersed from pre-defined

values than simulation results. For case 1, this dispersion in the experimental results is compatible with the error associated with each measurement.

Clamped-clamped aluminium beam

The same aluminium beam was now clamped on both sides. Table 3 shows the two considered pre-defined displacement fields and the optimal actuation voltages obtained in this case. The GA parameters were kept unchanged.

Table 3. Pre-defined displacement field and actuation voltages obtained by GA (clamped-clamped aluminium beam).

	Displacement Field	V_{piezo1} [V]	V_{piezo2} [V]	V_{piezo3} [V]
Case 1	$\gamma(x) = 0.00004(1 - \cos(\frac{2\pi x}{L}))$	-53	80	-56
Case 2	$\gamma(x) = 0.000075(1 - \cos(\frac{2\pi x}{L}))(\frac{x}{L})$	17	74	-121

Figures 5 and 6 show the comparison between the two pre-defined displacement fields, simulation results and experimental measurements.

Figure 5. Case1:clamped-clamped. Comparison between the pre-defined shape, simulation results and experimental measurements.

Figure 6. Case2:clamped-clamped. Comparison between the pre-defined shape, simulation results and experimental measurements.

For the first case, the desired shape is achieved with relatively small voltages, with piezoelectric elements 1 and 3 presenting identical voltage values: -53 Volt and -56 Volt respectively. For the second case, which corresponds to a non symmetry shape, the voltage level is higher in the piezoelectric element number 3, -121 Volt, and opposite in sign to the one of piezoelectric element number 1, +17 Volt. The standard deviation between the pre-defined results and the simulation ones and between the pre-defined results and the experimental ones was calculated. For case 1 values of 0.0018 mm and 0.0041 mm were obtained while for case 2 one obtains 0.0024 mm and 0.0033 mm, respectively.

As for the case of the clamped-free beam, experimental results are more dispersed from pre-defined values than simulation results. However, this dispersion in the experimental results is compatible with the error associated with each measurement and in general a very good agreement is obtained for both cases. The last two cases validates both the finite element code being used as well as the optimisation algorithm.

Experimental results: aluminium plate with 4 PZT

The shape control in two directions will be experimentally verified using a plate structure. The experimental set-up comprises an aluminium plate, 0.5 mm thick, with four bonded piezoceramics (electro-mechanical properties showed in Table 1). Figure 7 presents the layout.

Figure 7. Aluminium plate, 0.5 mm thick, used in the experiment. Units in mm.

Clamped-free aluminium plate

Table 4 shows the assumed pre-defined shape and the actuation voltages, obtained by GA, needed to apply to each of the four piezoelectric elements in order to achieve that same shape. The plate is intended to have a combined movement of bending and torsion.

Table 4. Pre-defined displacement field and actuation voltages obtained, by GA, for the clamped-free aluminium plate.

Displacement Field	V_{piezo1} [V]	V_{piezo2} [V]	V_{piezo3} [V]	V_{piezo4} [V]
$\gamma(x, y) = 0.0076x^2 + 0.0035xy + 0.00075x$	-68	-100	196	200

A population size of 25 individuals, a probability of crossover equal to 0.75, a probability of mutation equal to 0.20 and a maximum number of generations of 50000 were considered in the calculations. The voltages in each piezoelectric actuator were limited to -100 Volt and +200 Volt. Figures 8 and 9 show the comparison between the pre-defined displacement field, simulation results and experimental measurements, as function of the longitudinal co-ordinate, and respectively at the points $y=12$ mm and $y=36$ mm. Figures 10 and 11 show the comparison between the pre-defined displacement field, simulation results and experimental measurements at the points $x=60$ mm and $x=135$ mm, as function of the transversal y co-ordinate.

Experimental data follow much better simulation results than pre-defined ones. This means that, on one side, experimental measurements validate the simulations models but, on the other hand, the geometry may be too rigid, the layout of the piezoelectric actuators is not the best or the number of piezoelectric patches are not enough to induce the structure to deform in the correct and pre-defined way.

Fittings to the experimental and simulation data, obtained along y at the points $y=12$ mm and $y=36$ mm, were performed in order to understand how well the measured shape of the plate is closer to the pre-defined one. One can observe that, in general, the fitting to the simulation and experimental data follows, approximately, the same parabolic shape as the pre-defined displacement field. Namely, for $y=12$ mm $\chi^2=0.9985$ for the simulation data and $\chi^2=0.9967$ for experimental points.

Simulation results: optimal layout of piezoelectric actuators

The procedure developed so far assumed a specific layout of actuators and determined the optimal actuation voltages with respect to that layout. However the optimisation of the actuator location for achieving

Figure 8. Comparison between the pre-defined displacement field, simulation results and experimental measurements for $y=12$ mm.

Figure 9. Comparison between the pre-defined displacement field, simulation results and experimental measurements for $y=36$ mm.

Figure 10. Comparison between the pre-defined shape, simulation results and experimental measurements for $x=60$ mm.

Figure 11. Comparison between the pre-defined shape, simulation results and experimental measurements for $x=135$ mm.

a desired shape can be advantageous in order to minimise the error in the deflection. The extension of the GA optimisation code in order to include the best actuator location with respect to the fitness function was done. The optimisation problem consists now in finding a set of actuation voltages and the position, within the finite element mesh of the structure, of a limited number of piezoelectric actuators, subjected to certain values of saturation voltages, such that the desired shape of the structure is obtained. The optimisation algorithm was modified in order to accommodate two different types of information: the location of each piezoelectric element and the voltage needed to apply to each of them. So, the first part of each chromosome consisted in a binary variable with the information of a presence (1) or absence (0) of an actuator. This sequence was as long as the number of elements of the finite element mesh of the structure. The second part was a sequence of real numbers representing the actuation voltages. A population size of 20 individuals, a crossover probability of 0.75, a mutation probability of 0.15 and a maximum number of generations of 10000 was considered. The choice of an initial population was made based on educated guesses.

Clamped-free aluminium plate

This simulation aims at finding the location and the voltages of a fixed number of piezoelectric patches, glued in the clamped-free aluminium plate, in order to deform it according to the functions shown in

Figure 12. Case1: Pre-defined displacement field $\gamma(x) = 0.0012x + 0.003x^2$.

Figure 13. Case2: Pre-defined displacement field $\gamma(x, y) = 0.0015x + 0.01x^2 + 0.002xy$.

An aluminium plate, 144 mm long, 48 mm wide and 0.5 mm thick, together with a maximum number of piezoelectric elements (PX5-N from Philips Components) limited to 4 with 24 mm long, 12 mm wide and 0.3 mm thick was considered. The saturation voltages were limited to -100 Volt and +200 Volt. The finite element model of the plate consisted in 24 elements (6 longitudinal and 4 transversal). Each chromosome had a length of 28 variables; 24 binary values corresponding to a piezoelectric (1) or non piezoelectric (0) element and 4 real values corresponding to the actuation voltages. Figure 14 shows the results of the optimisation procedure concerning the location of the piezoelectric elements for case 1 and case 2 and Table 5 the corresponding optimal actuation voltages.

Figure 14. Optimal location of the 4 piezoelectric actuators for case1 and case2.

Table 5. Results concerning the optimal placement of the piezoelectric actuators, within the aluminium plate, and the corresponding actuation voltages obtained by GA.

	Piezoelectric Elements	V_{piezo1} [V]	V_{piezo2} [V]	V_{piezo3} [V]	V_{piezo4} [V]
Case 1	1 ; 7 ; 13 ; 19	57.5	45.9	43.4	52.9
Case 2	1 ; 3 ; 19 ; 23	88.2	25.7	120.5	82.0

Since there was no penalty, in the fitness function, of the increase of the weight due to the piezoelectric actuators the final optimal result, for both cases, assumes that all the four piezoelectric actuators are contributing to induce deformations in the structure. Case 1 consists in a bending movement of the whole plate independent of the y co-ordinate. The final result assumes that all piezoelectric actuators are located near the clamped edge of the plate where the strain energy and the effect of the actuators is

maximum. In case 2 the plate is intended to deform in bending and in torsion. This torsion movement can only be achieved, with this kind of piezoelectric material, if the piezoelectric actuators are displaced in a non symmetric manner in the plate or tilted relative to the longitudinal axis. The optimal result assumes that 2 piezoelectric actuators are located near the clamped edge, where their influence is maximum, and located opposite to each other, with different applied voltages, while the other two are also located in opposite sides but this time not symmetrically to each other and again with different actuation voltages, producing all together this bending plus torsion effect.

The comparison, along x and y directions, between the pre-defined shape and the shape obtained with the piezoelectric actuator layout of Figure 14 and with the actuation voltages of Table 5 are shown in Figures 15 and 16 for case 1 and in Figures 17 and 18 for case 2.

Figure 15. Case1: Pre-defined displacement field and simulation results ($y=24$ mm).

Figure 16. Case1: Pre-defined displacement field and simulation results ($x=144$ mm).

Figure 17. Case2: Pre-defined displacement field and simulation results ($y=24$ mm).

Figure 18. Case2: Pre-defined displacement field and simulation results ($x=144$ mm).

In both cases a very good agreement was found between the pre-defined shape and the simulation results; better than in the case concerning the experimental results of an aluminium plate with 4 piezoelectric actuators glued on it in a non optimal manner. As expected, case 1 corresponds to pure bending movement with no torsion. For case 2 (Figure 18) the torsion effect is visible and a difference less than 1% is found between the slope of the simulation results ($\alpha=0.0118$) and the pre-defined one ($\alpha=0.0117$).

CONCLUSIONS

A systematic and general methodology, using a finite element code and genetic algorithms, for the shape control and/or correction of static deformations of adaptive structures, was proposed and experimentally verified. Throughout this paper only glued piezoelectric elements are considered, however the developed methodology also supports embedded ones. Shape control was applied to a beam and plate structure with different boundary conditions. A good agreement was found between simulation and experimental results. The square root of the error between the nodal pre-defined displacement and the achieved displacement was considered as the objective function. With the aim of decreasing the errors between the pre-defined shape and the obtained shape of a structure the optimisation algorithm was modified in order to consider not only the determination of optimal voltages but also to optimise the best location of the piezoelectric actuators. The obtained results validate the adopted methodology.

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